

**THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF STEPHEN KRASHEN TO
LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AND TEACHING**

Abdullajonova Zumrad

Student, English Philology Faculty

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

E-mail: emerald2811@icloud.com

***Abstract.** The aim to write this academic work is to learn what Stephen Krashen thinks about language acquisition and his works and recommendations as he is known for developing a theory of second language acquisition that is commonly used in schools. We can find a lot of helpful information of him on all kinds of social medias to learn how to gain a new language in a fun and beneficial way.*

***Key words:** Language learning acquisition, second language learners, teaching theories, foreigner talk and motherese.*

Introduction. As more and more people have been paying attention to learn second language acquisition, more and more theories have been found and discussed among scientists and linguists. One of these linguists is Stephen Krashen. He is an American linguist who was born in 1941. He received PhD in Linguistics in 1972 and he has continued his career working as a linguistics professor at the University of Southern California. He has gained a number of awards and accolades by his work. He has received the Mildenerger Award and the Pimsleur Award for her writing, as well as the Dorothy C. McKenzie Award for her contribution. prominent in the field of children's literature. People have received her work with positive critical reviews, and her work has become the educational standard for second language learning in North America. Language monitoring method is one of the most important theories by Krashen which is so beneficial and important to influence the quality of input in classroom, and helpful to reduce anxiety, and enable students to appreciate their listening and comprehensive communicative competence in communication as his work has primarily focused

on his theory of second language acquisition, or the process through which individuals learn a language besides their native language.

Main part

Second Language Acquisition and Theories of Stephen Krashen

Second language acquisition is a major topic of discussion in this field of linguistics. Learning a second language has many advantages and many American parents want their children to learn a second language at school. In Krashen's work, he makes an important distinction between language learning and language acquisition. According to Krashen and, learning should be a deliberate process of reinforcing language skills through structured activities. Most people who have studied a second language are familiar with this approach. Krashen distinguishes learning from acquisition on the basis that acquisition is an organic process that comes about through an immersion environment. Understanding this distinction is critical for understanding Krashen's work, which can be divided into five hypotheses.

While I was learning language acquisition ideas of Stephen Krashen to write this work, as I always think learning new languages takes a lot of my time, effort and stress as well, I was just somehow shocked and happy because he claims that learning second language is similar to learn our own mother tongue as it is so easy to learn with more listening and speaking from our childhood. This requires meaningful interaction in the new language as natural communication in which speakers care about the messages they are conveying and understanding, not the grammar of the language. But Krashen recommends and demands that if someone is learning a new language, this person should pay more attention to be able to communicate in this language rather than studying complicated grammar forms or so on. He also thinks that, a native speaker of a language speaks with less complex sentences and modifies his/her speech into shorter to help second language learners. In the literature, this type of language learning is referred as “*foreigner talk*.” Mothers also makes their speech as easy as possible to help their children to understand them as they are learning their first language ever. This type is called

“*motherese.*” According to Krashen, we have two independent ways of developing language ability. One is language acquisition as a subconscious process and the second is a deliberate effort, as we learned in school. As it was mentioned above, Stephen Krashen claims that we learn primarily naturally in a way that does not require the rules and grammar ranges that does not help us so much. The second hypothesis is the natural order, which states that there is a natural order by which we acquire the elements of a language. It does not relate how simple or complex those particular grammar issues are. Studies have shown that a number of grammar issues in different languages see to be acquired in the same order and it does not really matter how much effort is put into teaching these. It is not because we have learned something that we acquire it, because there is a natural order, says Krashen.

Conclusion. From all this information I understand that Stephen Krashen finds easy approaches to learn a new language even though it is thought the most difficult one. And Krashen's ideas have revolutionized language teaching and remain influential in both theoretical research and practical classroom approaches. However, some of his ideas, such as the minimal role of explicit instruction, have sparked debate among educators and researchers.

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